

IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the main approaches to improving the management of the physical culture and sports complex of the republic. The great importance of propaganda in the development of physical culture, sports and a healthy lifestyle is noted.

Key words

Sport, physical culture, health, republic, management

In modern society, physical culture and sports occupy one of the main places in the development of a healthy and active population. In recent years, the cult of a healthy lifestyle among young people, as well as the older generation, has intensified in our country.

In the modern world, there is an increase in the economic and political function of the sphere of physical culture and sports, along with its social significance. The development of the physical culture and sports complex has a positive impact on all spheres of society, increasing human potential and human capital, creating additional factors for successful socio-economic development. In this regard, it is particularly important to improve the existing approaches to the management of the physical culture and sports complex.

There are a number of problems in the development of physical culture and sports:

- insufficient involvement of the population in systematic physical education;
- insufficient development of the material base and infrastructure of physical culture and sports, as well as its moral and physical aging;
- insufficient number of professional coaching staff;
- loss of traditions of Uzbek mass sports;
- lack of active promotion of physical culture and sports at the state level as an integral part of a healthy lifestyle, including taking care of the health of the future generation;
- gaps in the interaction of state executive authorities with local executive authorities of the subjects of the Republic and with public sports organizations in the field of physical culture and sports.

The propaganda direction is of decisive importance in the development of the sphere of physical culture and sports.

Propaganda is various forms (oral, printed, Internet, visual, etc.) of spreading and explaining ideas, teachings, views, theories that affect people's consciousness and mood. The promotion of physical culture implies purposeful activities to disseminate knowledge in the field of physical culture and sports, as well as to introduce the population to systematic physical culture and sports, as well as to lead a healthy lifestyle.

An important role in its successful achievement of the main objectives of propaganda is played by the correct formulation of information and propaganda work. To do this, it is extremely necessary to increase the level of physical education of the population; education of the need for the approval of a healthy lifestyle, the use of physical culture in the mode of work and rest.

By itself, the expression "Healthy lifestyle" includes such conditions as:

- ☑ regular physical education classes;
- ☑ rejection of bad habits and addictions;
- ☑ balanced nutrition;
- ☑ compliance with the daily routine;
- ☑ rational combination of physical activity with intellectual work;
- ☑ conducting classes in ecologically clean areas (mountains, forests, parks, river banks, etc.).

In other words, physical education does not guarantee positive results if any of these conditions are not met. Only compliance with an integrated approach to the implementation of all the principles of a healthy lifestyle entails the acquisition of moral and physical comfort.

According to the modern concept of WHO, human health implies a state of physical, mental and social comfort. Thus, physical education is only one of the sides of the process of educating a harmoniously developed personality, which should occupy a fairly significant part in the schedule of the daily routine of a modern person. An important factor of a healthy lifestyle is the implementation and compliance with medical recommendations for various diseases. The total denial of the achievements of modern medicine and the fascination with so-called "folk remedies" can cause irreparable harm to the body.

In our modern period of time, this problem has become more urgent, as the number of "office" workers who lead a sedentary lifestyle has increased. These people spend the whole day in a stuffy room and a confined space, are often in a state of high stress, and also travel by personal or official vehicles (all this contributes to the development of hypodynamia and chronic hypoxia in combination with instability of blood pressure and high lability of the nervous system). Even a passion for fitness and a visit to the gym after the end of the working day against the background of professional fatigue does not relieve the severity of the problem – such unsystematic loads only aggravate the chronic fatigue syndrome, which leads to a negative effect.

Physical culture and sports are one of the main areas of satisfaction of vital human needs in motor activity, ensuring the harmonious formation of personality.

The concepts of "Healthy lifestyle" and "Physical culture" are organically united in their humanistic orientation and are focused on the physical development and physical fitness of a particular person. Physical culture creates the necessary prerequisites and conditions for maintaining a healthy lifestyle of a person, an essential component of which is the organization of motor activity. Maintaining the body in a constant tone contributes to increased working capacity, creative activity, physical improvement, preservation of health and longevity.

Currently, Uzbekistan pays great attention to the promotion of physical culture, sports and a healthy lifestyle.

The adoption of regulatory and legal documents in the field of physical culture and sports makes it possible to clearly identify the goals, objectives and main directions in the field of promotion of physical culture, sports and a healthy lifestyle, to distribute powers and responsibilities, as well as to determine the basis of interaction between authorities.

At the same time, the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan also clearly traces the strategic target stated in the "Strategy for the Development of physical culture and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period up to 2030" – an increase in the share of citizens of the

Republic systematically engaged in physical culture and sports in the total population from 19 percent in 2020 to 30 percent by 2025, up to 40 percent in 2030, where one of the main conditions for the successful implementation of this plan is the development and effective implementation of a set of measures to promote physical culture and sports as the most important component of a healthy lifestyle. The program "Development of physical culture and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030" pursues the following goals: creating conditions that enable residents of the Republic to lead a healthy lifestyle, systematically engage in physiology of the population of the Republic; development of youth sports, high-performance sports and professional sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan; development of student sports in the Republic.

This document is a logical continuation of the implemented program "Development of physical culture and sports in the Republic for 2018 - 2020".

The Ministry of Tourism and Sports, the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, the Ministry of Public Education, the Ministry of Preschool Education, the Committee on Youth Policy and other executive authorities are engaged in the promotion of a healthy lifestyle, physical culture and sports in the village.

In the Republic, 15 Olympic reserve colleges, 7 RSHVSM (Republican schools of higher Sports skills), 254 youth sports schools (children's and youth sports schools) and 56 sports schools (specialized children's and youth sports schools) are working on the development of physical culture and sports among children, adolescents and youth. Along with the above-mentioned institutions, sports activities are carried out by a number of state higher educational institutions.

More than 3 million people are systematically engaged in sports sections, regardless of their departmental affiliation and organizational and legal form. The educational and training process in sports schools is carried out in 64 sports, including 35 Olympic sports. The Ministry of Tourism and Sports of the Republic, together with the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, territorial governing bodies of physical Culture and Sports, hold pageants: "For the best performance of physical culture and recreation and mass sports work among sports boarding schools", "For the best sports and recreation work at the place of residence", etc.

The territorial governing bodies of physical culture and sports annually hold mass physical culture and wellness events, holidays for preschoolers "Health Days", competitions among kindergarten teams within the framework of the "Fun Starts" program, review competitions for the best physical culture and wellness work in preschool institutions.

Many sports events are held in the summer: competitions among mahalla teams in various game sports, physical culture and sports; development of physical culture and sports among various groups republican tournament in various sports among rural teams, republican tournament for the prize "Leather ball" and others.

Every year, the Ministry of Tourism and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in accordance with the Unified Calendar plan of national and international physical culture and sports events, conducts more than 20 thousand physical culture and recreation and mass sports events among various categories of the country's population.

Many years of experience in conducting socially-oriented actions has shown that to ensure the effectiveness of the programs for a healthy lifestyle, it is not enough to organize one-day mass

sports events. It is necessary to involve all levels working with the population and youth, starting with preschool and school institutions and ending with the formation of a system of information, scientific and methodological support for activities aimed at promoting a healthy lifestyle, physical culture and sports.

According to the results of the study, a number of problems in the field of physical culture, sports and a healthy lifestyle in the Republic were identified, such as:

1. Only 20% of the country's residents are systematically engaged in physical culture and sports in the Republic.
2. Crisis of the sphere management system in the whole country.
3. Low efficiency of promotion of physical culture, sports and a healthy lifestyle by executive entities.
4. Ineffective promotion of physical culture, sports and a healthy lifestyle by the mass media.
5. The lack of systematic promotion of FCS and HLS in kindergartens, schools, educational institutions of secondary vocational and higher vocational education and labor collectives.
6. Lack of information support for physical culture and recreation and sports events held on the territory of the Republic.

The problem that I would like to focus on is the insufficient financing of the physical culture and sports industry in rural areas.

Without the active participation of local executive bodies in the development of sports at the mass level, it is impossible to increase the number of residents systematically engaged in physical culture and sports and leading

The following ways of increasing the effectiveness of the promotion of physical culture, sports and a healthy lifestyle on the territory of Uzbekistan are formulated.

1. Creation and broadcasting in educational institutions of the Republic and youth social networks of videos on the topic "Physical culture, sports and a healthy lifestyle". Placement on billboards of propaganda posters promoting physical culture and sports (according to the system of parallels – on one poster images of winners of local competitions and famous Uzbek athletes in the corresponding sport under the general motto "Your life! Your achievements! OUR victory!").
2. Production of stands and posters telling about the history of Uzbek sports, creation of portable exhibitions demonstrating the achievements of the country's athletes and their presentation at various competitions and official events. Also, the placement of information stands and posters in schools, institutions of primary, secondary and higher professional education.
3. Holding a competition in the Republic of "Uzbekistan – the territory of sports" in order to create a brand of Uzbek sports with its further use in the manufacture of uniforms for national teams of the Republic, as well as as an official symbol of Uzbek sports.
4. Holding conferences and round tables on the promotion of physical culture, sports and a healthy lifestyle on the territory of the Republic for various audiences: volunteers; students and students; heads of sports federations and public organizations; physical education teachers; heads of physical education departments of universities; heads of sports clubs at the place of residence.
5. Careful control over the conduct of physical culture and recreation, sports and promoting a healthy lifestyle events on the territory of viloyats, cities and fogs of the Republic.

6. The creation of a regional information center for the promotion of physical culture, sports and a healthy lifestyle covers:

- a statistical and diagnostic unit - such a center forms an information network, the elements of which are secondary educational schools, lyceums, colleges, technical schools, universities, youth schools, sports schools and other mass educational youth structures.;
- research unit - the involvement of scientific personnel in the region will provide ample opportunities for the development of innovative technologies in the field of physical health and sports activities of children and young people, and in general - in the field of saving the health of the younger generation;
- consulting unit - organization of a telephone consulting service on physical culture, sports and a healthy lifestyle;
- information block – organization and holding of seminars, master classes, conferences, trainings, PR campaigns, development of the center's website, which will host propaganda videos, information cards, scientific articles on physical culture, sports and healthy lifestyle, addresses of sports sections and family leisure places, announcements and results of the ongoing events;
- crisis unit – organization of an assistance service, a helpline, psychological counseling, in particular, for people with various kinds of addictions.

3. Of particular note is the promotion of physical culture, sports and a healthy lifestyle among children and adolescents.

Children are the future of every country, which is why physical development, physical fitness and health status of children and adolescents are especially important. They are the most suggestible audience, which is just forming life values and attitudes, lifestyle. It is very important to form the image of a successful person in children – healthy, physically developed, purposeful, independent, self-confident.

Advertising has a great influence on the children's audience with not well-established tastes, habits, with an unformed style and lifestyle in modern conditions, generating negative consequences.

Problem 1. Influence on the imagination. The interference of commerce constantly belittles the role of play and, as a result, children's imagination and imagination, limits the ability of children to think and act spontaneously.

Problem 2. Promotion of unhealthy food.

When it comes to food, children are the target group for advertising all kinds of products: from edible checkers - two-color cookies that can be played like checkers, to battery-powered lollipops. The amount

of time that children spend watching TV is usually indicated as the most important factor in the growth of cases of obesity in children.

Problem 3. Propaganda of "adulthood".

Attracting children to alcohol and tobacco. One of the new extremes in the field of marketing products in the youth market involves imposing adult products on teenagers, presenting products as funny and youth. First of all, it is advertising cigarettes and alcohol (beer).

To increase the effectiveness of the promotion of physical culture, sports and a healthy lifestyle among children and adolescents, the following activities are being implemented appropriately:

- carrying out physical culture and sports events "Sport for a healthy lifestyle!" in the form of a sports holiday for students of the Republic's secondary schools, with the participation of famous athletes, holding demonstrations of republican sports federations, including also weekly master classes for students from famous athletes of the country - winners and prize-winners of Olympic, continental and international competitions;
- holding a photo contest among schoolchildren promoting the FCS and healthy lifestyle "Sport for a healthy lifestyle";
- holding a drawing contest on the eve of the Olympic Games among students of secondary schools, as well as among pupils of preschool institutions;
- "Olympic relay race" among the territorial entities of the republic;
- an effective way to promote a healthy lifestyle and increase interest in regular physical education classes is holding sports competitions of different levels. In the school system of physical education, if we want to educate healthy children with the psychology of the winner, it is necessary to revive the principle of sportiness (competitiveness) by offering our students a well-thought-out system of school sports competitions.

- So, the promotion of physical culture, sports and a healthy lifestyle should certainly come to the fore. At the same time, it is necessary to pay attention to the development of mass physical culture, and sports of the highest achievements, and the conduct of socially significant propaganda events. Development and support of mass, public sports

They should be a priority, since mass physical culture contributes to improving the health of citizens and the quality of life, stabilizing civil society, spiritual and physical health improvement of young people, prevention of deviant social behavior. There are also opportunities for agitation and propaganda in big sports that need to be implemented: representatives of high-performance sports who are known not only in their country but also abroad, thanks to the interest in them from the media, can influence the formation of public opinion.

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